

MODERN PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN LEGAL EDUCATION

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***Annotation:** the article analyzes whether legal culture is an issue at the level of state policy, its importance in the development of the state and society, the issues of approaching legal education processes based on the educational cluster. Using examples of modern pedagogical approaches in legal training are described.*

***Key words:** legal education, legal state, obligation, civil society, comparative analysis, modern approaches, humanistic approach, educational cluster.*

Introduction

The main sign of a civil society and a legal democratic state is the education of people with a high legal culture. Clear, uniform and unwavering enforcement of laws depends on everyone's sense of duty and responsibility. Why "A perfect society can be built only by educating perfect people"[1]. Therefore, all countries approach the work of increasing the legal literacy of the population, especially the youth, as an issue at the level of state policy. In particular, in the early years of our independence, on November 20, 1991, the Law "On the Foundations of the State Policy Regarding Youth" was adopted (New version: September 14, 2016), the National Law on "Raising legal culture in our society" dated August 29, 1997 program", as well as documents such as "Concept of Raising Legal Culture in Society" approved by Presidential Decree No. PF-5618 dated January 9, 2019 "On Fundamental Improvement of the System of Raising Legal Awareness and Legal Culture in Society" it shows that special attention has been paid to the issue. We can see this situation in almost all countries of the world. In particular, in the Russian Federation, approved by the decree of the President of

April 28, 2011, "Basics of state policy in the field of legal literacy and legal awareness of citizens", approved by the decree of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, dated June 21, 1995, "Legal training of young people in the Republic of Kazakhstan" Documents as well as "concept of legal policy until 2030" of the Republic of Kazakhstan are proof of our opinion.

Analysis of resources on the topic

In all societies of our time, pedagogues, jurists, and intellectuals are conducting research on improving legal education tools and methods, using different approaches to achieve legal literacy of the population. For example, in Uzbekistan, M.A. Atavullayev, H.T. Mamatov, R.E. Turdiboyeva, E.O. Kadyrov; In Russia, R.V. Antropov, T.S. Dondokov, M.V. Sahakyan; In Kazakhstan, G.R. Absattarov, B.K. Nurgazinov, S.A. Sartaev; In Japan, the research of Setsuo Miyazawa and other scientists can be highlighted. Educating the young generation in a free, democratic and humanitarian spirit, raising them in the spirit of a perfect human being, and protecting and ensuring their rights and freedoms is very important for every society that aims to build a democratic, legal state based on civil society. and is of actual importance [2]. Indeed, solving the problems of this field is a factor that solves existing shortcomings in societies, as well as prevents them. In scientific legal resources, there are three different classifications of the legal culture of society members:

a) simple legal culture - belongs to members of society whose legal views are formed empirically;

b) professional (occupational) legal culture - applies to employees who work directly in judicial and legal institutions. When talking about this issue, it is appropriate to pay attention to the following fact: "There is currently 1 lawyer per 100,000 residents of the republic within the framework of a single law firm," the Republic of Uzbekistan informs. Minister of Justice Ruslan Davletov in his report [3].

c) scientific legal culture - belongs to pedagogues teaching legal subjects in educational institutions, scientists conducting research in the field of law.

Admittedly, this indicator is significantly lower in many societies. This can be seen in the example of social events taking place in different regions of the world. M.V. Sahakyan, an employee of the Department of Philosophy and Sociology of Astrakhan State University, says that "Unfortunately, it is difficult to include the level of legal culture of Russian society not only in the high, but also in the average level of legal culture [4].

Research methodology

In the preparation of the article, objectivity, historicity and comparative analysis methods were used, and scientific researches and electronic resources in the fields of pedagogy and methodology were used as a basis.

Analysis and results

Legal education and training materials, introduction of effective approaches in this process is the demand of today. Therefore, the article aims to reveal the importance of developing legal education based on the educational cluster system and through modern pedagogical approaches.

Educational cluster means the strategic cooperation of production, service and other institutions related to its activity around one scientific and educational center for joint development. How to apply the cluster system to legal education? This implies the use of methods that serve to achieve the harmony of theory and practice in the processes of legal education. For example, legal studies should be organized in the building of the court, law enforcement agencies based on the content of the subject, students and young people may participate as direct observers in the possible proceedings, get acquainted with the personal attitude of employees with practical experience, and the practice of students in the same way. Ensuring their organization in institutions, moreover, it is manifested in the conduct of cooperation between law enforcement bodies and universities. Only if, in the subject of constitutional law, the parliament's powers are directly familiarized with the parliament building and its activities, and a roundtable discussion is organized with the parliament's employees (deputies), or in the family law, if it is organized in real terms with the activities of

civil status registration bodies, the effectiveness of the lesson, it serves the formation of specific skills and independent thinking in students. The educational cluster in civil law can be used as follows:

- students learn how to apply to state and non-state organizations independently;
- direct familiarization with the Charters of legal entities of various forms;
- conclusion of civil legal contracts, monitoring of notarial confirmation processes;
- participation in civil court proceedings;
- strengthen their knowledge of the subject by asking questions to practitioners (judge, prosecutor, lawyer, etc.);
- getting to know working documents related to rights and legal capacity in archive departments, etc.

Achieving "Teacher-student-practice cooperation" in all classes of legal sciences serves to improve legal literacy to a certain extent.

The issue of approaching the issue of legal culture on the basis of the cluster system is expressed in paragraph 1 of the program approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2124 dated February 6, 2014.

In addition, the issue of widespread introduction of modern approaches to education has been studied by many of our pedagogic scientists, and the issue of directing it to the field of legal sciences is also in front of us. In modern pedagogy, the following main types of approach to education are distinguished:

Cultural approach. In the implementation of this approach, the basis of the educational process is to refer to national culture and traditions. It is impossible to imagine the upbringing of the culture of the young generation without taking into account the psychological structure, traditions, rituals, and holidays of each nation. The problems of educating students cannot be solved without relying on the moral and ethical values of the people. A modern teacher cannot fulfill his task without relying on folk pedagogy, without instilling in the young generation a sense of respect for the traditions, language and culture of his people.

For example, a comparative analysis of the norm "Everyone has the right to education..." in Article 50 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and its inclusion in our national legal system, "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the child. It is appropriate to rely on hadiths such as "Learn science even if it is from China", "Education is obligatory for every Muslim man and woman" (Some countries have certain conditions for continuous education). For example, in South Korea, a citizen who has been active in another field of social life for more than 5 years is not admitted to the educational system. Basically, according to the above norm, he can apply to a higher educational institution. an educational institution in our country is possible at any age.) Through this approach, students not only learn about constitutional law, but also strengthen their knowledge of the state and legal theory (the science of legal sources), and also serve to improve their legal knowledge. culture.

Value approach education is focused on values, among which young people often have a desire for truth, social justice, honesty and dignity, benevolence and humanity for their own health and those around them, willingness to help, opinion and there is a desire to respect differences and so on. In the preparation of legal subjects, the detailed disclosure of these issues related to each subject serves to increase the activity of students and the mood of connection to the subject. For example, in many places, the rule of "committing other actions not prohibited by law" established by legal norms supports free entrepreneurship. But in practice, there are cases where this standard is misunderstood or not used at all.

Humanistic approach. In his opinion, a person, an educated person, is a supreme value that has the right to live, to be happy, to live worthy of living. Rights and freedoms of the child, his free and creative development and self-development are the priorities of humanitarian pedagogy.

Individual oriented approach. In the context of person-oriented education, as a general principle, a certain final goal - an ideal model of a person - is taken. All other components of the educational system, the conditions for its operation and self-development are developed and implemented taking into account the given final result.

Using this approach in legal sciences is very effective. For example, the selection of problem situations related to the topic in matters related to the life of listeners and students' daily activities serves to increase their interest and interest;

Personal-activity approach. This approach implements the idea that the development of a person is carried out in activities. At the same time, activity is considered through a system of components: needs, motives, actions, conditions, operations, results.

It serves to strengthen the knowledge of students by participating in conference events, scientific olympiads, independent scientific projects and various scientific exams on topics studied in the field of law. This encourages the student to work more on his knowledge and skills.

Conclusion

Legal consciousness and legal culture are one of the integral and basic forms of social consciousness and serve as a guarantee of the well-being of the society and the stable development of the country. In this regard, it is necessary to approach the system of raising legal culture on the basis of an educational cluster, to achieve the appropriate participation of representatives of all sectors in this process. There is no doubt that the participation of educational institutions, educational administration and other state and non-state organizations, various public associations will serve the effectiveness of the activity.

The widespread use of modern pedagogical methods in the processes of legal education attracts the attention of students and guarantees its effectiveness. The widespread introduction of these issues into pedagogical practice requires a correct attitude from every member of society.

RESOURCES

1. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev. Yangi O‘zbekiston strategiyasi. Toshkent – 2021. 421-bet.
2. M.N.Khushnazarova. “Theoretical and methodological basis of training of management personnel in the process of higher pedagogical education”. International journal of social science & Interdisciplinary research. 11.04 (2022): 171–177
3. R.Davletov. Oliy Majlis Qonunchilik palatasining navbatdagi majlisidagi ntqidan 17.10.2023. ([https://uza.uz/oz/posts/100-ming-aholiga-bir-nafar-advokat-togri-
keladi_301780](https://uza.uz/oz/posts/100-ming-aholiga-bir-nafar-advokat-togri-
keladi_301780))
4. М.В. Саакян. Пути повышения правовой культуры российского общества. (<https://cyberleninka.ru>)
5. M.A.Atavullayev. “Jamiyatni modernizatsiyalashda huquqiy qadriyatlarning o‘rni”. 09.00.02 – Ong, madaniyat va amaliyot shakllari falsafasi (huquq falsafasi)./ Shifr: Dis-2020/68-30-2019.
6. X.T.Mamatov. “Huquqiy madaniyat va O‘zbekistonda fuqarolik jamiyatining shakllanish muammolari” 12.00.01 – Davlat va huquq nazariyasi va tarixi; siyosiy va huquqiy ta’limotlar tarixi Shifr: Dis-878/2012
7. Turdiboyeva R. E. “Talaba yoshlarda huquqiy madaniyatni shakllantirish muammolari” dis.... yuridik. fan. nomzodi: 12.00.00/ Shifr: Dis-6435/2000
8. Р.В.Антропов. Ц.С.Дондоковю Правовая культура как важнейший элемент правовой системы общества: понятие и особенности в немецкой правовой доктрине
9. Абсаттаров Г.Р. Приоритеты правовой культуры республики Казахстан: политологические аспекты. (ip1.ru)
10. S.Miyazawa For the Liberal Transformation of Japanese Legal Culture: A Review of Recent Scholarship and Practice. www.researchgate.net/publication